

A Hospital-Based Comparative Study on Direct Lateral Approach and Posterior Approach in Management of Fracture Neck of FemurAbhilash Kumar¹, Channabasava², Subhash Patil³, Kanakachalapathi⁴, Amaresh⁵¹Junior Resident, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India.³Associate Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India⁵Junior Resident, Department of Orthopedics, Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur, Karnataka, India

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Abstract:**Aims and Objective:** 1. To compare the advantages, complications, morbidity, mortality rates associated with each of the procedures. 2. To study the recovery to physical independence in each of the procedures with respective approaches. 3. To compare results with other studies**Methodology:** a Retrospective study of 42 patients undergoing hemiarthroplasty in Department of orthopaedics in Raichur institute of medical sciences, Raichur, Karnataka from September 2022 to September 2023**Results:** Of the 42 participants, 17 (77.3%) of the individuals were female, while 5 (22.7%) were male performed LA [lateral approach], similarly 15 (75%) of the subjects were female, while 5 (25%) were male performed PA [posterior approach]. The average length of surgery in the lateral group was 70±15 minutes, while in the posterior group it was 90 ± 15 minutes which was found statistically significant, LA patients found less blood loss compare to PA patients which was statistical significance. The lateral group had a mean drain output of 90 ± 48 ml, while the posterior group had a mean drain output of 150 ± 22 ml. The difference in Drain Output between groups was significant. 2 % of the lateral group and 10% of the posterior group experienced dislocation. The lateral group's median hospital stay was 6 days, while the posterior group's median hospital stay was 9 days which was found statistical significance. Post-operative pain was completely mild in both groups: the lateral group (22) and the posterior group (20). In our current study, infection was found in 13.6% of the lateral group and 15% of the posterior group. There was no statistically significant relationship between pain and infection rate among groups. The post-operative mobilization was immediately on POD 2 in hardinges approach whereas it was POD 5 in post-approach groups which were statistical significance.**Conclusion:** This study indicated that there was statistically significant difference in rate of dislocation, length of surgery, blood loss between the lateral and posterior approaches for hemiarthroplasty of the hip joint. However early mobilization on the second day in the majority for the lateral group, early mobilization on the 5th day in the majority for the posterior group, there was a substantial difference in hospital stay duration between the groups and participants of both groups showed mild pain.**Keywords:** FNF [fracture neck of femur], LA[lateral approach], PA [posterior approach], hardinge's, hemiarthroplasty.

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Introduction

One of the more frequent fractures in the body, FNF [femoral neck fracture] makes for roughly 3.6% of adult fractures. FNF, which typically refers to a fracture in the area of the femoral head that extends to the base of the femoral neck, is more prevalent in elderly people. Due to an ageing population and

changes in lifestyle, the prevalence is increasing quickly. Hemiarthroplasty of the hip was originally introduced in 1940 by Moore and Bohlman, then by the Austin-Moore endoprosthesis. Thompson unveiled a similar endoprosthesis in 1954. Moore first suggested utilizing a posterior surgical

approach to install his prosthesis. Following that, other hip procedures were carried out, most notably the anterior and anterolateral approaches. The 1954 description of a comparable technique by McFarland and Osborne has gained popularity in recent years because to Hardinge's description of a straight lateral approach to the hip joint. Hemiarthroplasty (HA) of the hip joint is a common treatment option for fracture neck of the femur intracapsular. Without the possibility of avascular necrosis or non-union, which are frequent side effects of internal fixation, HA enables immediate full weight-bearing. Additionally, HA leads to less reoperations in individuals over 60 years old as compared to internal fixation.

The majority of femoral neck fractures require surgery. Stress fractures on the compression side of the neck and femoral neck fractures in individuals who are non-ambulatory and comfortable or who are too frail for surgical therapies are potential exceptions.

The patient's physiological age heavily influences the implant and surgery options. Hemiarthroplasty or complete hip replacements are used to treat elderly patients with displaced femoral neck fractures. One of the most often performed orthopedic operations is hemiarthroplasty for hip fractures. Each year, more than a million of these operations are performed worldwide.

The surgery may be performed using any one of many surgical techniques, including the anterior, antero-lateral, lateral, and posterior. The lateral and posterior route is now the two methods most often utilized for hip hemiarthroplasty. The posterior technique is frequently used since there is less injury to the hip muscles and a better recovery. Compared to the posterior approach, the anterior and lateral methods are less likely to result in a dislocation.

HA is the ideal treatment for people who are institutionalized, have cognitive disabilities, and/or have restricted physical activity. Contrarily, there is little agreement on which treatment is preferable—HA or PTH—in self-sufficient, physically active people with normal cognition. Additionally, there are two HA options: unipolar and bipolar.

Aims and Objectives

1. To compare the advantages, complications, morbidity, mortality rates associated with each of the procedures.
2. To Study the recovery to physical independence in each of the procedures with respective approaches.
3. To compare results with other studies.

Materials and Methods

Patients undergoing Hemiarthroplasty in Department of Orthopaedics at the department of

orthopaedics, Raichur institute of medical sciences, Raichur-584103

Study Population: Patient undergoing hemiarthroplasty of hip joint procedure by

Posterior approach and lateral approach for fracture neck of femur a retrospective study

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with age group >50 yrs of either sex
2. Low energy, non-pathological fragility cervical hip fracture.
3. Patients who give informed consent to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

1. Immobility (mobile with wheel chair or bed bound)
2. Pathological fractures
3. Moderate to high energy hip fractures
4. Patients with Acetabular arthritis
5. Patients with active infection

Steps in Lateral Approach (Hardinge Approach)

1. Anaesthesia – spinal or epidural anaesthesia
2. Position of the patient- lateral decubitus
3. Land mark- palpate anterior superior iliac spine. Palpate the lateral aspect of the greater trochanter and, below that, the line of the femur that feels like a resistance against the examining hand.
4. Incision - Begin the incision 5 cm above the tip of the greater trochanter. Make a longitudinal incision that passes over the center of the tip of the greater trochanter and extends down the line of the shaft of the femur for approximately 8 cm
5. inter nervous plane- There is no true inter nervous plane. The fibers of the gluteus medius muscle are split in their own line distal to the point where the superior gluteal nerve supplies the muscle. The vastus lateralis muscle is also split in its own line lateral to the point where it is supplied by the femoral nerve.
6. Superficial surgical dissection- Incise the fat and underlying deep fascia in line with the skin incision. Retract the cut edges of the fascia to pull the tensor fasciae latae anteriorly and the gluteus maximus posteriorly.

Detach any fibers of the gluteus medius that attach to the deep surface of this fascia by sharp dissection. The vastus lateralis and the gluteus medius are now exposed.

7. Deep surgical dissection- Split the fibers of the gluteus medius muscle in the direction of their fibers beginning in the middle of the trochanter.

Do not go more than 3 cm above the upper border of the trochanter because more proximal dissection

may damage branches of the superior gluteal nerve. Split the fibers of the vastus lateralis muscle overlying the lateral aspect of the base of the greater trochanter.

- Next, develop an anterior flap that consists of the anterior part of the gluteus medius muscle with its underlying gluteus minimus and the anterior part of the vastus lateralis muscle.
- Continue developing this anterior flap, following the contour of the bone onto the femoral neck, until the anterior hip joint capsule is fully exposed. Develop the plane between the hip joint capsule and the overlying muscles, using a

swab pushed into the potential space using a blunt instrument.

- Enter the capsule using a longitudinal T-shaped incision. Osteotomize the femoral neck. Extract the femoral head using a corkscrew.

8. Dangers - The superior gluteal nerve runs between the gluteus medius and minimus muscles approximately 3 to 5 cm above the upper border of the greater trochanter.

More proximal dissection may cut this nerve or may produce a traction injury

Figure 1: Skin incision, 2: Tensor fascia lata, 3: Gluteus medius

Steps in Posterior Approach (Moore's Approach)

1. Anaesthesia –spinal /epidural
2. position-lateral decubitus
3. Land mark -Palpate in detail the greater trochanter on the outer aspect of the thigh. The posterior edge of the trochanter is more superficial than the anterior and lateral portions, and, as such, it is easier to palpate
4. Incision-Make a 10- to 15-cm curved incision centered on the posterior aspect of the greater trochanter. Begin incision some 6 to 8 cm above and

posterior to the posterior aspect of the greater trochanter. The part of the incision that runs from this point to the posterior aspect of the trochanter is in line with the fibers of the gluteus maximus. Curve the incision across the buttock, cutting over the posterior aspect of the trochanter, and continue down along the shaft of the femur

5. Inter nervous plane- There is no true inter nervous plane in this approach. However, the gluteus maximus, which is split in the line of its fibers, is not significantly denervated because it receives its nerve supply well medial to the split

6. Superficial surgical dissection- Incise the fascia lata on the lateral aspect of the femur to uncover the vastus lateralis. Lengthen the fascial incision superiorly in line with the skin incision, and split the fibers of the gluteus maximus by blunt dissection

7. Deep surgical dissection- Retract the fibers of the split gluteus maximus and the deep fascia of the thigh. Underneath is the posterolateral aspect of the hip joint, still covered by the short external rotator muscles, which attach to the upper part of the posterolateral aspect of the femur

- Internally rotate the hip to put the short external rotator muscles on a stretch (making them more prominent) and to pull the operative field farther from the sciatic nerve
- Insert stay sutures into the piriformis and obturator internus tendons just before they insert into

the greater trochanter. Detach the muscles 1 cm from their femoral insertion and reflect them backward, laying them over the sciatic nerve to protect it during the rest of the procedure

- The posterior aspect of the hip joint capsule is now fully exposed. The hip joint capsule can be incised with a longitudinal or T-shaped incision

8. Dangers -The sciatic nerve is rarely exposed or transected during this approach. However, it is sometimes involved in major complications. It can be damaged if it is compressed by the posterior blade of a self-retaining retractor used to split the gluteus maximus. Always keep the retractors on the cut surfaces of the rotators; the muscles will protect the nerve.

Figure 3: Patient position, 4: Skin incision, 5: Tensor fascia lata and gluteus maximus incision

Results

Of the 42 participants, 17 (77.3%) of the individuals were female, while 5 (22.7%) were male performed LA [lateral approach], similarly 15 (75%) of the subjects were female, while 5 (25%) were male performed PA [posterior approach]. The average length of surgery in the lateral group was 70 ± 15 minutes, while in the posterior group it was 90 ± 15 minutes which was found statistical significance, LA patients found less blood loss compare to PA patients which was statistical significance.

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Figure 6: Pie- chart showing gender distribution in the study population (n=42)

Figure 7: Chart showing distribution of selected cases

Below Chart Showing Duration of Surgery in both Direct Lateral Approach and Posterior Approach

Table 1: General characteristics of the parameters in the present study

Parameter	Lateral approach group	Posterior approach group	P value
Mean ± SD average length of the surgery (minutes)	70 ± 15	90 ± 15	<0.05
Mean ± SD drain output (ml)	90 ± 48	150 ± 22	< 0.05
Dislocation (%)	2	10	< 0.05
Hospitalization (days)	6	9	< 0.05
Post-operative pain (number of patients)	22	20	>0.05
Infections (%)	13.6	15	>0.05

Discussion

Femoral neck fractures treated with hemiarthroplasty using a direct lateral vs. posterolateral approach:

Hip arthroplasty, with hemiarthroplasty (HA) being the most popular choice, has replaced reduction and

internal fixation as the preferred method of therapy for displaced femoral neck fractures (FNF) [49]. The direct lateral (DL) and posterolateral (PL) surgical methods are the two most common techniques used in hip replacement surgery. In FNF patients, the DL technique is associated with a decreased dislocation rate and a lesser requirement for revision surgery

and however, there hasn't been much research done on how surgical techniques affect hip function and quality of life in FNF. The PL strategy was linked to a superior patient-reported result when compared to the DL in patients with osteoarthritis (OA) who were having hip arthroplasty. The greater prevalence of gluteus medius insufficiency and trochanteric pain with the DL method has been blamed for this discrepancy. The literature does not fully address the presence and impact of gait abnormalities brought on by various surgical techniques in FNF treated with hip arthroplasty.

In the literature, the comparison of the PL and DL methods in THA for OA patients is well established. The majority of studies show no discernible difference between the two strategies in terms of functional result or postoperative morbidity. The PL method, however, was found to have a somewhat superior functional outcome and reduced 90-day mortality in investigations employing the National Joint Registry of England and Wales. In studies utilizing the Swedish Hip Arthroplasty Registry, discovered a reduced risk of revision owing to aseptic loosening whereas discovered a greater rate of revision due to dislocation using the PL method. Less research has been done on these variations in hip arthroplasty for FNF patients.

For instance, even when restoration of the posterior soft-tissue structures was carried out, Enocson et al., 2008 observed that the PL approach was the main risk factor that increased the dislocation of HA. Additionally, Sköldenberg et al found that switching from the PL strategy to the DL approach significantly reduced the rate of prosthesis dislocation. In a retrospective cohort analysis, discovered that both the DL and PL techniques had a similar risk of early surgical problems, with the DL approach inclined to instability and the PL approach predisposed to hematoma development. On the other hand, Keene and Parker observed greater postoperative infection rates, blood loss, and surgical time with the DL technique and increased risk for thrombosis with the PL approach.

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